

at 1190 cm^{-1} may be assigned to tertiary amino group of dimethyl moiety⁷. This band was shifted to 1100 , 1100 , 1110 and 1110 cm^{-1} for the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes respectively. This suggests the involvement of tertiary nitrogen atom of the group in complexation. Since the bands due to $\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ mixed stretching vibrations found in the ligand at 1585 and 1550 cm^{-1} were shifted in the complexes near 1525 and 1505 cm^{-1} , the nitrogen atom of pyridine ring is also involved in the complexation^{8,9}. The sharp band at 1705 cm^{-1} in spectra of the ligand may be due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ of maleate ion. It was reported⁶ that some bands observed in the region $1160-1060\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to pyridine vibrations. In the present case similar bands were observed in the ligand and the complexes but they were of quite weak intensity. The band near 780 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the ligand and the complexes has been assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-Cl}}$ ⁶. The band near 475 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ ^{10,11}. The weak bands at 384 , 380 , 375 and 250 cm^{-1} in the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes respectively may be assigned to coordinated N atom of pyridine ring. The bands at $300-220\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes may be assigned to $\text{M}-\text{Cl}$ ^{12,13}.

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Studies on Coordination Polymers. Part-II.

Polymeric Complexes of Di(*o*-aminophenyl)disulphide with Nickel(II), Cobalt(II), Manganese(II) and Chromium(III)

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SOME polymeric complexes in which nitrogen and sulphur donor atoms are present, have been studied in this laboratory¹. The present communication records the synthesis and characterisation of a tetradentate ligand di(*o*-aminophenyl)disulphide (1) containing two sulphur and two amino groups and its complexes with Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and Cr^{III} .

1

Experimental

o-Nitrobenzenethiol (NBT): A mixture of *o*-nitrochlorobenzene (15.8 g, 0.1 mol) and thiourea (7.8 g, 0.1 mol) in ethanol was refluxed till all the thiourea had dissolved. The solution was distilled under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was recrystallised using petroleum ether-ethanol mixture, dried and analysed (Table 1).

Di(*o*-nitrophenyl)disulphide (DNPS): A mixture of *o*-nitrobenzenethiol (15.6 g, 0.01 mol), 1N NaOH (140 ml) and iodine (12.6 g) was refluxed for 6 h. Air was then bubbled through the solution for 4 h and the resulting yellow solid was recrystallised and analysed (Table 1).

Di(*o*-aminophenyl)disulphide (DAPS): DNPS (6.16 g) and Raney nickel (0.5 g) were suspended in methanol and hydrazine hydrate (~5 ml) was added dropwise with refluxing and constant stirring. On cooling the resulting brown solid was crystallised from acetone and analysed (Table 1).

Preparation of metal complexes: To a suspension of appropriate metal salt (0.01 mol) in xylene (50 ml), the ligand DAPS (2.48 g, 0.01 mol) was added and the solution was refluxed for 10-14 h. The solvent was then distilled off and the resulting solid was crystallised from petroleum ether, dried and analysed (Table 2).

Molar conductance (DMSO), ir spectra, magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectra were explored to characterise the complexes. Solubility

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF NBT, DNBS AND DAPS

Compd.	Colour	Yield %	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			
				C	H	N	S
NBT	Yellow	60	190	46.15 (46.45)	3.28 (3.26)	8.92 (9.03)	20.48 (20.65)
DNBS	Yellow	90	148	46.68 (46.75)	2.42 (2.60)	8.89 (9.09)	20.58 (20.78)
DAPS	Brown	80	161	53.18 (53.06)	4.78 (4.84)	11.16 (11.29)	25.69 (25.81)

*Uncorrected.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND LIGAND FIELD DATA OF POLYMERIC COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/ (Calcd)		μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ_M^* Ω^{-1} $cm^2 mol^{-1}$	Dq (cm^{-1}) Found/ (Calcd.)	B cm^{-1}	β	ν_2/ν_1
	M	N						
$[-Ni(L)(H_2O)_2 -]_n Cl_{2n}$	14.49 (14.25)	6.26 (6.76)	2.04	142.06	976.0 (999.0)	1 014.0	0.94	1.55
$[-Ni(L)(H_2O)_2 -]_n (SO_4)_n$	13.69 (13.44)	6.16 (6.38)	3.14	160.21	1 053.0 (891.0)	909.0	0.98	1.38
$[-Ni(L)(H_2O)_2 -]_n (CH_3COO)_n$	13.12 (12.79)	6.29 (6.07)	3.21	155.36	988.0 (893.0)	911.9	0.91	1.39
$[-Co(L)(H_2O)_2 -]_n Cl_{2n}$	14.91 (14.25)	7.52 (6.76)	4.02	165.16	1 157.5 (1 084.0)	1 129.8	1.01	1.44
$[-Co(L)(H_2O)_2 -]_n (SO_4)_n$	13.72 (13.44)	6.81 (6.38)	4.09	137.62	1 111.0 (1 040.7)	1 084.0	0.97	1.73
$[-Co(L)(H_2O)_2 -]_n (CH_3COO)_n$	13.11 (12.79)	7.19 (6.07)	4.57	152.39	1 190.0 (1 114.5)	1 160.9	1.04	1.83
$[-Mn(L)(H_2O)_2 -]_n Cl_{2n}$	13.98 (13.41)	7.03 (6.83)	5.94	161.34	1 661.0 (1 662)	677.9	0.66	1.37
$[-Mn(L)(H_2O)_2 -]_n (SO_4)_n$	13.09 (12.64)	6.02 (6.44)	6.17	159.64	1 730.0 (1 729.0)	706.1	0.68	1.31
$[-Mn(L)(H_2O)_2 -]_n (CH_3COO)_n$	12.91 (12.04)	6.49 (6.18)	6.37	162.04	1 562.0 (763.6)	694.1	0.72	1.45
$[-Cr(L)(H_2O)_2 -]_n Cl_{2n}$	12.25 (11.75)	6.62 (6.33)	4.10	234.62	1 389.0 (751.2)	682.9	0.71	1.98
$[-Cr(L)(H_2O)_2 -]_n (CH_3COO)_n$	10.81 (10.14)	6.15 (6.46)	3.96	235.29	1 454.0 (716.4)	651.3	0.68	1.34

*In DMF.

of the complexes was determined in 3% concentration in various solvents. All the complexes were soluble in DMF and DMSO but insoluble in methanol, acetone, chloroform and water.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes (Table 2) suggest their polymeric formulae to be $[-M(L)(H_2O)_2 -]_n X_{2n} Y_n$ and $[-Cr(L)(H_2O)_2 -]_n X_{2n}$ where, L=DAPS; X=Cl⁻, CH₃COO⁻; Y=SO₄²⁻. Very large values of molar conductance (Table 2) in DMF support their electrolytic nature.

In the IR bands of the ligand DAPS at 3 300–3 280, 1 650–1 400 and 800–650 cm⁻¹ are due to ν_{NH_2} , mixed C=C ring stretch, in-plane and out-of-plane CH deformations and ring deformations respectively. The very sharp band at 950 cm⁻¹ is due to the ν_{CS} vibrations. In the spectra of complexes, the ν_{NH} band appears at 3 240 ± 10 cm⁻¹ and the aromatic ring vibrations at slightly higher position, suggesting the coordination³. As reported for many similar complexes, the usual coordination through sulphur splits the ν_{CS} band into two components—at 960 ± 5 and 730 ± 10 cm⁻¹. In the

present complexes however, the former band is not observed at all but only the latter band appears around 735 cm⁻¹. This result is an outcome of the formation of polymeric structures in which both the sulphur atoms are involved in coordination, but to different metal ions³. The coordination of water is inferred by the presence of OH stretching, rocking and wagging bands at 3 360, 890 and 700 cm⁻¹ respectively⁴. The spectra of free ligands do not show any band below 600 cm⁻¹, while the complexes show two sharp bands at 430 ± 5 and 290 ± 5 cm⁻¹ assigned to M–S and M–N stretches thereby confirming the coordination of the ligand through both its nitrogen and sulphur atoms⁵.

The ¹H nmr spectra of the ligand show one triplet at δ 7.20 (phenyl ring protons) and one multiplet at δ 4.60 (NH₂). In the complexes these signals shift in the ranges δ 7.50–7.80 and 4.70–4.90 due to coordination.

The μ_{eff} values (Table 2) show that complexes are high-spin in nature with a pseudo-octahedral environment around the metal ion⁶. The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes show three bands

around 27.00, 15.50 and 9.50 kK corresponding to three octahedral transitions, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3). There is a very strong charge transfer absorption around 39.00–41.00 kK which obscures the ν_3 transition. Both the ν_2 and ν_1 bands show pronounced splitting with two distinct components, confirming the pseudo-octahedral structures with approximate D_4h symmetry⁷. In the spectra of the Co^{II} complexes, bands centered around 9.00, 15.00 and 22.50 kK are observed which are assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions of distorted octahedral symmetry⁸. The spectra of the Cr^{III} complexes show bands at 15.50 and 33.50 kK assigned to be due to ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) and ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) transitions of octahedral symmetry⁹. In the spectra of the Mn^{II} complexes ν_3 , ν_2 and ν_1 bands are seen at 24.00, 15.00 and 11.00 kK corresponding to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6T_{1g}$ (4G), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}$ (4G) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6T_{1g}$ (4P) transitions. Their position and weak intensity correspond to distorted octahedral geometry¹⁰.

The values of all the ligand field parameters have been calculated using standard equations (Table 2) which are also in agreement with the octahedral structures of the complexes. The large Dq values are probably an outcome of the stability conferred in the complexes due to the formation of polymeric structures while the B and β values show sufficient degree of covalent character on metal-ligand bond involving some pi-type interaction¹¹.

In order to get a relative idea of the thermal stability of these polymeric complexes, their thermooxidative degradation was studied by thermogravimetry. These data show that the heat resistance temperatures of these lie in the range 250–300°. The initial weight-loss ($8 \pm 2\%$) at $320 \pm 10^\circ$ corresponds to the coordinated water in the complexes. The complexes exhibit reasonable stability upto 450°, as these do not melt but slowly darken to black powder after 24 h.

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Outersphere Association of Cobalt(III) Complexes: α, α' -Dipyridyl-bis-biguanidecobalt(III) and *o*-Phenanthroline-bis-biguanidecobalt(III) Salts

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NUMEROUS data have been published on outersphere association of cobalt(III) complexes. But there are hardly any literature data for the composition and stability of outersphere cobalt(III) complexes other than hexamine¹⁻⁵, tris-ethylenediamine^{1,2,6,7}, acidopentamine⁸ and acidotetramine^{9,10} cobalt(III) complexes. This investigation is undertaken to fill partly the above gap in the chemistry of cobalt(III) outersphere complexes. In continuation of our previous study¹¹ we report herein the conductance behaviour of α, α' -dipyridyl-bis-biguanidecobalt(III) and *o*-phenanthroline-bis-biguanidecobalt(III) chloride, bromide, iodide and sulphate salts in dilute aqueous solution at 25° in terms of Onsager's theory and also determine their outersphere association constant. The association constants were found to increase in the order: $\text{SO}_4^{2-} \gg \text{Cl}^- \gg \text{Br}^- \gg \text{I}^-$. However Pyartman *et al.*¹² studied the following system: (i) $[\text{Rh}(\text{phen})_3] \text{L}_3^{3-n}$ ($\text{L} = \text{I}^-, \text{Br}^-$), (ii) $[\text{Rh}(\text{DMF})_6]^{3+} \text{L}^-$ ($\text{L} = \text{HCOO}^-, \text{OAc}^-, \text{EtCOO}^-, \text{PrCOO}^-$) and (iii) $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})_2]^{3+} \text{L}^-$ ($\text{L} = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{ClO}_4^-$), where they obtained the result opposite to that predicted from electrostatic theories of ion association. They explained these results by considering the hydrophobic properties of cationic complexes.

Experimental

α, α' -Dipyridyl-bis-biguanidecobalt(III) and *o*-phenanthroline-bis-biguanidecobalt(III) chloride were